

Pancreatic Tumor Segmentation in Therapeutic and Diagnostic MRI: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Pancreatic Tumor Segmentation in Therapeutic and Diagnostic MRI

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

PANTHER

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Pancreatic cancer is among the most aggressive and lethal malignancies, with a 5 year survival rate of only 10-12%. The poor prognosis is largely due to late detection, rapid disease progression, and the difficulty of complete surgical resection. Medical imaging plays a central role in improving patient outcomes by enabling early detection, accurate staging, and precise treatment planning.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is particularly valuable for pancreatic cancer management due to its superior soft tissue contrast. This capability allows for detailed visualization of tumors, adjacent organs, and neurovascular structures—essential for assessing resectability and guiding treatment strategies, such as surgical resection or neoadjuvant therapies. MRI is also critical in radiation therapy planning, where accurate delineation of tumors and organs at risk improves treatment precision and patient outcomes, especially in MR-Linac systems. These systems integrate real time MRI with radiation delivery, enabling adaptive treatments. However, precise and efficient segmentation of the pancreas and tumors remains a bottleneck in clinical workflows.

Manual segmentation of pancreatic tumors is time consuming and labor intensive, particularly when transitioning between diagnostic MRIs (high quality imaging used for initial assessment) and MR-Linac images (real time treatment imaging). Annotating MR-Linac data is further complicated by lower image quality and modality differences. The current workflow often involves transferring delineations from diagnostic scans to treatment scans using registration algorithms, a process that introduces delays and potential inaccuracies that need to be manually corrected. This challenge stems from the scarcity of annotated MR-Linac datasets, which difficult the development of robust AI segmentation models tailored to this modality.

The purpose of this challenge is to advance cross-domain learning for pancreatic cancer segmentation. By leveraging annotated diagnostic MRIs alongside a limited number of annotated MR-Linac images, participants will develop models capable of accurate and robust segmentation across both domains. A key goal is to reduce reliance on manual delineations and registration workflows, ultimately accelerating treatment planning and

enhancing clinical efficiency.

The challenge will provide a training set comprising annotated diagnostic MRIs, unlabeled multi-sequence MRIs, and a smaller set of annotated MR-Linac images. Separate test sets for diagnostic MRIs and MR-Linac images, ensuring robust evaluation of performance.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Pancreatic cancer, Magnetic Resonance, MR-Linac, Segmentation, Radiation Therapy, Artificial Intelligence

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The novelty of the challenge lies in its focus on pancreatic cancer segmentation using both diagnostic MRIs and MR-Linac images, evaluated as distinct tasks. This approach addresses the significant lack of publicly available MRI datasets for pancreatic tumors and the even greater scarcity of annotated MR-Linac data. By leveraging annotated and unannotated diagnostic MRI data as well as a limited number of annotated MR-Linac images, the challenge explores whether segmentation models can achieve high performance on these two clinically relevant modalities, each with differing characteristics (e.g., T1-weighted contrast-enhanced vs. T2-weighted non-contrast), and with varying levels of data availability.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

1. Task 1: Segmentation on Diagnostic MRIs

- Application Scenario: Accurate segmentation of pancreatic tumors on contrast enhanced diagnostic MRIs is essential for detection, staging, and treatment planning. Models developed for this task can streamline the process of tumor delineation, reducing radiologist workload and ensuring consistency in tumor assessment.

2. Task 2: Segmentation on MR-Linac MRIs

- Application Scenario: Precise segmentation of pancreatic tumors on MR-linac images is critical for real time radiotherapy planning and adaptive radiation treatments. Automating this process enables faster and more accurate delineation of target regions, improving treatment precision and reducing delays in therapy delivery.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

A half day session is required to allow the top performing teams to briefly present their methods and approaches. Following the presentations, the session will conclude with the announcement of the PANTHER challenge overall winner. This format provides an opportunity for participants to showcase their work, fostering knowledge exchange and discussion while ensuring the event remains concise and engaging.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

The expected participation for this challenge is approximately 100-200 participants with close to 15 teams making final submissions. This estimate is based on data from similar challenges: FLARE 2023 (47 teams, 292 participants), the Universal Lesion Segmentation Challenge (865 participants, ~13 final teams) and the Panorama Challenge for Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma detection (386 participants, ~20 final teams). We expect a strong level of engagement from researchers working on AI solutions.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results in a peer reviewed journal to summarize the outcomes, methodologies, and insights from the challenge. Up to three members from each of the three winning teams per task and the overall winning team will be invited to co-author the final challenge paper, provided they played a significant role in the design and implementation of their algorithms.

Participants are free to independently publish their algorithms and findings once the challenge concludes and an embargo period for the challenge summary paper is over. Any such independent publications must reference the challenge paper and any associated data publication papers to ensure proper credit and context for the work. After the challenge is finalized, its webpage on the grand-challenge platform and GitHub repository will remain active as enduring resources. We plan to link the final publication on these platforms and share publicly available participant codes along with methodology reports for their algorithms.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The challenge will be hosted on the grand-challenge.org platform. The public training dataset will be available for download via Zenodo, and participants will use their own computational resources for model training. Submissions will be made as Docker containers, and inference will be run offline on grand-challenge during the Development and Testing phases, with results evaluated and ranked accordingly.

TASK 1: Pancreatic tumor segmentation in diagnostic Magnetic Resonance Imaging

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) plays a critical role in the management of pancreatic cancer, particularly following detection or suspicion raised by computed tomography (CT). MRI is often performed to provide improved detection, assessment, and treatment planning. Among the various MRI phases, contrast enhanced T1 weighted arterial phase imaging offers superior tumor visualization, making it invaluable for accurately assessing tumor location, size, and relationship to surrounding structures. Segmentation of these images is essential for treatment planning and monitoring tumor progression. Automating this process with AI has the potential to significantly reduce radiologist workload and minimize variability in tumor delineation, ensuring consistent and efficient clinical workflows.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Pancreatic cancer, Magnetic resonance, Artificial intelligence, Segmentation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Amparo Soeli Betancourt Tarifa, Radiotherapy department, Radboudumc, The Netherlands

Peter Koopmans, Radiotherapy department, Radboudumc, The Netherlands

Faisal Mahmood, Department of Oncology, Odense University Hospital, Denmark

Uffe Bernchou, Department of Oncology, Odense University Hospital, Denmark

Anne Bisgaard, Department of Oncology, Odense University Hospital, Denmark

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Amparo Soeli Betancourt Tarifa, Radiotherapy department, Radboudumc, The Netherlands

amparosoeli.betancourttarifa@radboudumc.nl

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The website is still under construction but will be found at <https://panther.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

In the event of acceptance, we will seek sponsorship to provide prizes for the top performing methods. Depending on the availability of sponsorship, we plan to offer prizes for the top 3 models per task and an additional prize for the best overall team across all tasks.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

During the Development Phase, the performance and rankings of all submitted AI algorithms will be made public via the challenge's leaderboard. After the final submission deadline for the Testing Phase, the corresponding final leaderboard will also be publicly available on the challenge website.

The evaluation metrics and scoring system will be officially announced at the release of the challenge, ensuring

full transparency. All individual metric values and the scores that define the ranking will be visible to participants. The results will be formally announced at the MICCAI 2025 challenge session, where the top three teams per task and the overall winner will be invited to present their methods and results.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

a) Authorship in the Final Challenge Paper: Up to three members from each of the top three performing algorithms per task and the overall winning team will be invited as co-authors, provided they played a significant role in the design and implementation of their model.

Additionally, teams whose submissions demonstrate notable scientific relevance or innovation may also be invited to contribute to the publication.

b) Independent Publication of Results: Participating teams are encouraged to publish their own results independently after the challenge concludes. Any such publications must include proper citations of the challenge summary paper and relevant data publication papers to ensure proper acknowledgment of the challenge and its resources.

c) Embargo Period: An embargo period of 4 months will be enforced following the conclusion of the challenge. During this time, the challenge organizers retain exclusive rights to publish the collective results and findings. Once the embargo period ends, participants may proceed with their individual publications.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Participants must submit their models as Docker containers via the Grand Challenge platform, following the specific guidelines provided for this challenge.

During the Development Phase, submissions will be evaluated on a hidden validation cohort, and team rankings will be updated on a live, public leaderboard. In the Testing Phase, participants will submit a single AI algorithm encapsulated in a Docker container for final evaluation on a hidden testing cohort. These results will be used to determine the final rankings and the top performing teams.

To support participants, a baseline algorithm for each task will be provided through a GitHub repository, along with instructions on how to package the model into a Docker container. This will serve as a foundation for participants to customize and improve their models. Additionally, evaluation scripts—which will be used for final ranking—will be released and linked on the grand-challenge webpage, enabling participants to understand the final evaluation methods.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

The challenge will consist of two phases:

1. **Development Phase:** This preliminary phase allows participants to test and evaluate their algorithms on a small validation set. Teams will be allowed to submit up to 10 times during this phase.

A live leaderboard will display performance metrics and rankings based on validation data, enabling teams to improve their models. However, results from this phase will not contribute to the final ranking. The goal of this phase is to familiarize participants with the submission process and refine their models.

2. **Testing Phase:** In the final phase, each team will submit a single algorithm for evaluation on the hidden testing cohort. This one-time submission will determine the official performance metrics and final rankings of the challenge.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1st - April 30th , 2025

Introduction Workshop: A virtual session covering the clinical challenges of pancreatic cancer imaging, PANTHER's objectives and MR-Linac imaging will be held in the first week of the challenge release.

GitHub Repository Release: The challenge's GitHub repository will be made available in the first week, containing:

- Baseline implementation- Example code for a complete baseline solution for each task, including Docker containerization.
- Evaluation scripts – The scripts used for ranking participant submissions.

Dataset Release: The dataset will be released in three sequential stages to facilitate model development and evaluation:

- April 1st – The training dataset (with and without annotations) will be released. This will allow participants to begin model development and conduct preliminary evaluations.
- June 1st – The validation set will be released(without annotations) and participants can analyze their performance on live leaderboards.
- July 13th – The test dataset (without annotations) will be released for final evaluation.

Submission deadline: July 15th , 2025

Results announcement: September 23rd – 27th , 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The institutional review board of Radboudumc has waived the need for informed patient consent, for the retrospective scientific use of anonymized clinical data in this study.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation software, including functions for metrics calculation and ranking, will be publicly released via PANTHER's GitHub repository, ensuring full transparency in how submissions are evaluated. This code will also be linked on the challenge's webpage in the Grand Challenge platform.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams must submit their Docker containers along with a technical report or a short arXiv paper on their methodology to be eligible for ranking on the final leaderboard. These reports or preprints will be publicly released to promote reproducibility, and teams will be strongly encouraged to make their code open source to ensure credibility of all proposed solutions and promote open-source AI development.

Publicly available algorithms and papers on the challenge methods will be linked on PANTHER's GitHub repository and on its Grand Challenge webpage.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is funded by Radboudumc. Amparo Soeli Betancourt Tarifa acknowledges financial support from Elekta.

Access to the test set labels will be available for the challenge organization team during collection and preparation of the datasets.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Treatment planning, Intervention follow up, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Localization, Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this task consists of adult patients (18 years and older) with suspected or confirmed pancreatic cancer undergoing MRI for diagnosis, staging, or treatment planning. This population typically includes patients with pancreatic lesions at various stages, with the goal of enhancing segmentation accuracy to support preoperative evaluation and treatment response monitoring.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of retrospective MRI scans from patients with pathology confirmed pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC). All patients in this cohort underwent diagnostic MRI as part of their clinical care. The annotated dataset includes contrast enhanced T1-weighted arterial phase MRIs, which provide high soft tissue contrast and are used for tumor visualization, staging, and treatment planning. These were selected from cases where radiology reports confirmed tumor visibility and provided measurements, allowing for confident delineation of the pancreas and tumor.

In contrast, unannotated scans may include cases where tumors are harder to visualize due to imaging sequence limitations, subtle tumor presentation, or lower contrast. Many of these images come from the same patients but represent different sequences, such as non-contrast-enhanced or venous phase MRIs, where the tumor is less distinct.

This combination ensures diversity in the dataset, reflecting the range of cases encountered in clinical practice.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

This challenge task is based on contrast enhanced MRI, specifically axial T1 weighted arterial phase images. Non contrast enhanced, venous and delayed phase MRIs are also included in the dataset but are unlabeled, as tumor visibility is lower in these sequences.

All imaging data consists of axial views only. Sagittal and coronal reconstructions are not available at any stage of the challenge.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

- MRI scanner vendor and model for all patients included in the public training, hidden validation, and secret testing cohorts.
- Manually annotated segmentations of the following structures will be provided for all patients in the public training cohort:
 - Pancreas (parenchyma).
 - Tumor.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

- Patient age (years) for all patients in the public training, validation and test sets.
- Patient sex assigned at birth (male/female).

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Pancreas shown in contrast enhanced T1 weighted arterial phase MRI of the abdomen, with additional non contrast, delayed and venous phase MRIs of the upper abdomen. The challenge cohort consists of patients with pathology confirmed PDAC, while the target cohort represents patients undergoing abdominal MRI for diagnosis, staging, or treatment planning of pancreatic cancer.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms output target is the Segmentation of pancreatic tumor lesions.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Develop highly accurate segmentation algorithms for pancreatic tumor lesions in MRI scans., Achieve fast prediction times to ensure models can be seamlessly integrated into clinical workflows, while minimizing computational resource consumption.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

All images were acquired using SIEMENS MRI scanners.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All scans that will be annotated were acquired using a contrast enhanced T1-weighted arterial phase MRI protocol. Non-annotated scans include venous phase, delayed phase, and non-contrast MRI sequences.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

This retrospective study includes abdominal MRI scans, acquired between 2013-2021, at Radboud University Medical Center.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All acquisitions were performed by trained MRI radiographers with expertise in abdominal imaging protocols.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to an MRI scan.

- Training cases consist of annotated contrast enhanced T1 weighted arterial phase scans, along with unlabeled additional sequences such as venous, delayed, or non-contrast scans.
- Validation and test cases consist exclusively of contrast enhanced T1-weighted arterial phase MRI scans, with voxel level annotations for evaluation purposes.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

- Training Set:
 - 95 annotated cases (1 image per patient)
 - ~350 cases without annotations (possibly more than one image per patient)
- Validation Set: 6 cases (1 image per patient)
- Testing Set: 35 cases (1 image per patient)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

This distribution reflects a balance between annotated data (for supervised learning) and unannotated data (to leverage semi-supervised or self-supervised approaches), which is crucial for addressing the complexity and variability of PDAC in MRI. It also ensures that the model benefits from extensive training while maintaining sufficient data for evaluation and validation.

o Training (70%): A larger training set allows the model to better capture the heterogeneity of pancreatic tumors, crucial for improving segmentation accuracy. Additionally, the unlabeled data provides the opportunity to train a robust model.

o Validation (~4%): This proportion provides a reasonable number of cases to assess model performance on unseen data, considering that this phase is primarily intended to help participants familiarize themselves with the submission process.

o Testing (~26%): The test set is large enough to provide a reliable final evaluation, simulating real-world performance on unseen data. We will ensure that the test data is representative, including cases with varying tumor sizes and characteristics to better reflect clinical diversity and robustness in model evaluation.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The dataset for this task is designed to reflect the real-world distribution of patients suspected or diagnosed with pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC), the most common primary pancreatic malignancy, accounting for approximately 90% of all pancreatic cancers. Ensuring AI algorithms are trained and validated on a representative cohort of PDAC patients is essential for clinical translation and deployment.

- **Training Set:** The training set consists of patients with pathology confirmed PDAC. It includes contrast enhanced T1 weighted arterial phase MRIs with annotations, complemented by unannotated MRI sequences (venous, delayed, and non-contrast). The annotated arterial phase images focus on tumors with clear visibility, while the unannotated sequences can provide additional variability to improve model robustness.
- **Validation and Test Sets:** The validation and test sets will include recent scans from pathology confirmed PDAC cases, ensuring that the data reflects the latest imaging protocols and scanner technologies. These sets will feature a range of tumor sizes to better replicate the variability encountered in clinical practice.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All data used in this challenge consists of unpublished and previously unseen MRI scans. The dataset includes approximately 450 cases, covering the full training, validation, and test sets.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

- The test set will be annotated to the highest standard to ensure reliable evaluation of AI performance and enable direct comparison with experts. Tumor delineations will be performed by radiologists and radiation oncologists with extensive experience in pancreatic cancer imaging, ensuring precise segmentation that reflects clinical practice. Recognizing that inter-rater variability is inherent in clinical practice, each test image will be independently annotated by at least two specialists. This approach not only allows us to quantify the variability between annotators using overlap or distance metrics but also provides the opportunity to generate a consensus ground truth.
 - For the training and validation sets, an experienced radiologist will perform the initial annotations of the pancreas and tumor. In situations where the images present challenging or ambiguous cases, these annotations will be reviewed and refined in collaboration with a second specialist. This process ensures consistency and accuracy in the training and validation cohorts while maintaining a practical annotation workflow.
- Overall, the annotation process involves a minimum of three annotators. For the test set, two independent specialists will each provide annotations for every case to capture interobserver variability. Additionally, one expert is dedicated to annotating the training and validation sets (with challenging cases reviewed by a second specialist). There is also the possibility of involving more annotators if available.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotators are provided access to a reader study on the Grand Challenge platform, where they can review T1-weighted arterial phase MRI scans for each patient. For the entire dataset (train, validation and test), annotators are instructed to manually delineate the tumor based on the accompanying radiology reports. In the training set, an AI-generated pancreatic mask is preloaded for each case; the annotator is then tasked with reviewing and, if necessary, correcting this mask to ensure accuracy.

A comprehensive user guide detailing the annotation workflow and how to use the Grand Challenge platform has been provided to all annotators. This guide covers essential tasks, including navigation of the platform, creation of segmentation masks, interaction with AI-generated pancreatic masks, and procedures for manual correction.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The annotation process is performed by medically trained experts with extensive experience in abdominal imaging, pancreatic cancer diagnosis and treatment.

For the training and validation sets, a primary annotator, a radiologist with over five years of experience in abdominal MRI, is responsible for reviewing and correcting preloaded AI-generated pancreatic masks and generate tumor masks. In cases of uncertainty or challenging anatomy, a secondary specialist is consulted to ensure label quality.

For the test set, each case is independently annotated by at least two experts, radiologists and/or radiation oncologists, each with more than five years of professional experience in pancreatic cancer imaging. This multi-expert approach for the test set not only establishes a robust reference standard for AI evaluation but also allows for the quantification of interobserver variability.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

For the test set, each image is independently annotated by at least two specialists. Their annotations are merged into a consensus ground truth using a fusion method—such as majority voting, weighted average or an algorithm like STAPLE—to reconcile any discrepancies and provide a unified reference standard. This approach mitigates inter-rater variability and ensures a robust benchmark for evaluating AI performance. For the training and validation sets, a single high quality annotation is provided for each case, so no merging is required.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raw training, validation, and testing data are converted from DICOM to MHA format to reduce dataset size and undergo an anonymization process. No additional pre-processing is applied.

Participants are responsible for defining their own pre-processing pipelines to suit their models.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

For the entire dataset, there are inherent error sources related to image annotation that may affect the final segmentation of PDAC lesions:

General Sources (Applicable to All Sets):

- **Ambiguous Tumor Boundaries:** PDAC lesions often have poorly defined edges, making it challenging to accurately delineate their full spatial extent.
- **Tumor Heterogeneity:** Variations in tumor texture and composition can lead to differences in interpretation, affecting segmentation consistency.

Training and Validation Sets:

- **Intra-Annotator Variability:** Even with strict guidelines, a primary annotator may exhibit minor inconsistencies over time when segmenting the same lesion.
- **Consultation Discrepancies:** In challenging cases, when a secondary specialist is consulted, differences in interpretation can contribute to inconsistencies.

Test Set:

- **Inter-Rater Variability:** Although the test set is annotated by multiple experts (radiologists and radiation oncologists) and a consensus ground truth is generated, some variability remains, as reflected in overlap metrics such as the Dice coefficient.
- **Intra-Annotator Variability:** Even among experienced annotators, slight differences may occur when delineating the same lesion at different times, which can affect the final consensus despite efforts to mitigate it.

Overall, while our annotation protocol is designed to reduce variability, the inherent challenges in delineating PDAC lesions mean that it can still influence the final annotations. Notably, these error sources are also encountered in everyday clinical practice.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

In addition to annotation variability, several other factors contribute to potential errors in the segmentation of tumor lesions:

- **Imaging Artifacts and Quality Variability:** Motion artifacts, noise, and low signal to noise ratio (SNR) can obscure lesion boundaries. Older scans may have lower resolution and reduced image quality compared to more recent acquisitions, as MRI technology and scanning protocols have advanced over time. This discrepancy in image quality may introduce inconsistencies in segmentation performance across the dataset.
- **Tumor Size and Location:** Small or infiltrative tumors are often difficult to detect and delineate, particularly when located near vascular structures or at the pancreas' edges.

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The evaluation of algorithms will be based on a combination of overlap, boundary, and volumetric metrics to ensure a comprehensive assessment of segmentation performance. Emphasis will be placed on tumor segmentation metrics, reflecting the clinical importance of accurately delineating pancreatic tumors. Additionally, a score will be assigned to inference time to highlight its significance in real-life scenarios.

1. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC): Measures the spatial overlap between predicted and ground truth segmentations for both the pancreas and tumor.
2. 5mm Surface Dice: Evaluates boundary accuracy by calculating the Dice coefficient within a 5mm tolerance around the segmentation surface.
3. Mean Average Surface Distance (MASD): Measures the mean of averaged minimum distances between boundaries of predicted and ground truth segmentations.
4. Hausdorff Distance 95% (HD95): Captures the 95th percentile of the maximum boundary distances between the predicted and ground truth segmentations.
5. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) on Tumor Burden: Quantifies the error in tumor volume estimation.
6. TimeScore: A custom metric designed to assess the algorithm's inference speed. This metric incorporates a predefined maximum acceptable inference time (T_{max}), which represents the clinical threshold for inference time per volume for each task. Models with low segmentation accuracy do not receive a time based advantage, as a minimum Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC_{min}) must be met before the TimeScore is applied. This ensures that fast but inaccurate models are not rewarded unfairly.

For models meeting the minimum accuracy requirement ($DSC_{model} > DSC_{min}$), the TimeScore is computed using the following formula:

$$TimeScore = \max(0, 1 - T_{model}/T_{max})$$

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The selected metrics are designed to comprehensively evaluate the performance of segmentation algorithms, focusing on spatial overlap, boundary accuracy, and volumetric precision—key aspects for accurately segmenting tumors. Additionally, the metrics include a consideration of model inference time to reflect practical applicability.

1. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC): Is the most widely used metric for medical image segmentation as it measures the spatial overlap between predicted and ground truth segmentations. High DSC values indicate accurate segmentation, which is essential for delineating tumors. Overlap accuracy directly impacts surgical margin definition and tumor localization during treatment planning.
2. 5mm Surface Dice: This metric assesses segmentation accuracy within a clinically acceptable tolerance (5mm) around the boundary, aligning with the precision required for radiotherapy and surgical interventions.
3. Mean Average Surface Distance (MASD): Measures the mean of minimum distances between segmentation boundaries. Lower MASD values ensure accurate tumor boundary delineation, which is crucial for surgical planning and radiation therapy targeting in pancreatic tumors.
4. Hausdorff Distance 95% (HD95): The 95th percentile Hausdorff distance evaluates the largest segmentation errors while reducing the influence of outliers. This metric identifies cases where segmentation deviates significantly from the ground truth, ensuring that large errors in tumor boundary delineation are penalized. It reflects the need for consistent and reliable segmentation across the entire structure.
5. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) on Tumor Burden: Quantifies the error in tumor volume estimation, a critical factor for assessing tumor progression, treatment response, and surgical planning. Accurate tumor volume measurements are essential for monitoring disease progression and determining patient prognosis.
6. Time Score: Scores the algorithm's inference time according to clinical needs. This is particularly important for applications like online treatment with MR-Linac systems where the ability to produce rapid predictions within clinically acceptable timeframes is essential for real time adaptation and precision. The metric ensures models are evaluated not only for accuracy but also for their practical applicability in time sensitive workflows.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

a) The performance ranking for all participant algorithms will focus exclusively on tumor segmentation metrics and inference time, reflecting the clinical priority of accurately identifying and delineating pancreatic lesions within a clinically relevant time.

To rank the performance of the teams for each task, we employ a final score equation that integrates the above mentioned metrics, each assigned a specific weight to ensure the total sum equals 1. For all submitted algorithms, we first compute the individual metric values separately for each test case in the evaluation set. After evaluating all cases, we calculate the average value of each metric across the entire set, yielding a single value per metric. The final score is determined by combining these averaged values using a scoring equation with normalization formulas that scale all metrics to a 0 to 1 range before applying weights and adding them.

Tumor segmentation metrics account for 90% of the total score, while the Time Score contributes 10%, striking a balance between segmentation accuracy and inference efficiency. This allocation prioritizes both clinical relevance and practical applicability, ensuring that models are not only accurate but also feasible for real world deployment. The overall winner will be determined by the average score across both tasks.

The score for each task will be calculated as:

$$\text{Score} = w1 * \text{DSC_tumor} + w2 \text{SurfaceDice_tumor} + w3 * \text{MASD_score} + w4 * \text{Hausdorff95_score} + w5 * \text{RMSE_score} + w6 * \text{TimeScore}$$

SCORE COMPONENTS:

- Weight assignments : The weight for each metric sum to 1 and are assigned as follows :

- o w1 (DSC_tumor weight) : 0.3

- o w2 (5 mm Surface Dice) : 0.25

- o w3 (Mean Absolute Surface Distance Score) : 0.1

- o w4 (Hausdorff Distance 95 Score) : 0.1

- o w5 (Root Mean Square Error Score) : 0.15

- o w6 (Time Score) : 0.1

- DSC_tumor (Dice Similarity coefficient): value range [0,1]

- SurfaceDice_tumor (5 mm Surface Dice): value range [0,1]

- MASD_score (Mean Absolute Surface Distance Score): Represents the normalized and transformed MASD value, ensuring that lower MASD values result in higher scores within the [0,1] range. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{MASD_score} = \max(0, (\text{MASD_90th} - \text{MASD_tumor}) / (\text{MASD_90th} - \text{MASD_min}))$$

Where :

- o MASD_90th represents the 90th percentile of MASD values from all participants. This value is used to ensure that extremely poor performances do not disproportionately impact the normalization process.

- o MASD_min is the smallest MASD value (most accurate) obtained by the participants .

- o MASD_tumor is the MASD obtained by the participant.

- o The max function is applied to ensure the score remains non negative, preventing invalid scores from participant's whose MASD exceeds the 90th percentile.

- Hausdorff95_score (Hausdorff distance (95%) Score): Represents the normalized and transformed Hausdorff Distance(95%) value, ensuring that lower values result in higher scores within the [0,1] range. It is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Hausdorff95_score} = \max(0, (\text{Hausdorff_90th} - \text{Hausdorff_tumor}) / (\text{Hausdorff_90th} - \text{Hausdorff_min}))$$

Where:

- o Hausdorff_90th represents the 90th percentile of Hausdorff Distance values from all participants. This value is used to ensure that extremely poor performances do not disproportionately impact the normalization process.
- o Hausdorff_min is the smallest HD95 value (most accurate) obtained by the participants .
- o Hausdorff_tumor is the HD95 obtained by the participant.
- o The max function is applied to ensure the score remains non negative, preventing invalid scores from participant's whose HD95 exceeds the 90th percentile.

• RMSE_score(Root Mean Square Error on tumor burden's Score): This score represents the normalized and adjusted RMSE value, ensuring that models with lower RMSE values receive higher scores within the [0,1] range. The RMSE score is computed as follows:

$$\text{RMSE_score} = \max(0, (\text{RMSE_90th} - \text{RMSE_tumor}) / (\text{RMSE_90th} - \text{RMSE_min}))$$

Where:

- o RMSE_90th denotes the 90th percentile of RMSE values among all participants, acting as an upper limit to mitigate the influence of extremely poor performances.
- o RMSE_min represents the smallest RMSE value (best value) obtained by any participant.
- o RMSE_tumor is the RMSE value for the participant's model.
- o The max function is applied to ensure the score remains non negative, preventing models with RMSE values above the 90th percentile from receiving negative contributions.

• TimeScore : value range [0,1]

b) In the event of a tie among the best performing models for each task, the participant with the highest TieBreaker Score will be selected, calculated as:

$$\text{TieBreaker Score} = 0.5 * \text{SurfaceDice} + 0.5 * \text{TimeScore}$$

If the tie occurs for the overall winner, the TieBreaker Score will be calculated separately for each task, and the final decision will be based on the average TieBreaker Score across the tasks.

The TieBreaker Score balances boundary precision (5mm Surface Dice, 50%) and efficiency (Time Score, 50%), ensuring the winning models are both clinically accurate and practical for clinical application.. In case there is also a tie on this score, the team that submitted their algorithm first will be ranked higher.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Since the final score is based on the average values of each metric across all test cases, any empty predictions will negatively impact the overall score. If a model fails to produce a segmentation for a test case, all its metrics will be set to 0, lowering the average metric values and, consequently, the final score.

To further penalize models that fail to generate predictions without disqualifying them, an additional penalty is applied based on the number of missing cases:

$$\text{Penalized Score} = \text{Score} \times (1 - \text{missing cases} / \text{total cases})$$

This ensures that models with more missing predictions receive a lower final score, discouraging submissions that lack robustness in generating segmentation results.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking scheme is designed to balance segmentation accuracy with practical inference time, ensuring that models are clinically applicable while also encouraging computational efficiency. The chosen weights reflect the importance of each metric in tumor segmentation, particularly their relevance to treatment planning,

radiotherapy targeting, and surgical decision making.

To ensure a fair and meaningful contribution to the final score, distance-based error metrics (MASD, Hausdorff Distance 95, and RMSE) are normalized, so that lower error values (indicating better segmentation accuracy) result in higher scores. This normalization allows these metrics to be directly comparable to DSC and Surface Dice, which inherently range from 0 to 1.

Each metric's weight is carefully assigned based on its clinical significance and practical impact:

- DSC (0.3) and Surface Dice (0.25) are given the highest weights as they directly measure overlap accuracy and boundary precision, which are crucial for tumor delineation.

- MASD (0.1), HD95 (0.1), and RMSE (0.15) are included to account for boundary accuracy and overall segmentation error, ensuring that models with good overlap but poor boundary precision are not overly rewarded.

- Time Score (0.1) is incorporated to encourage efficiency, ensuring that highly accurate models are also practical for clinical workflows.

By balancing overlap based metrics, boundary precision, and computational efficiency, this ranking system ensures that top scoring models provide both accurate and clinically useful tumor segmentations while remaining computationally feasible for real world application.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The statistical test used for comparing AI submissions will be the permutation test.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The permutation test is a robust and reproducible method for comparing AI segmentation algorithms. It evaluates the likelihood that one algorithm outperforms another while accounting for variability in performance across different cases. By randomly shuffling predictions or performance metrics between algorithms, the test generates a distribution of results to assess if observed differences are statistically significant. This method is widely used in medical imaging and AI evaluation, making it well suited for fair and unbiased comparison of AI submissions in this challenge.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 2: Pancreatic tumor segmentation in MR-Linac Imaging

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Linear Accelerators (MR-Linacs) are advanced radiotherapy systems that combine real time magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with a linear accelerator (Linac) for delivering radiation. This integration allows clinicians to visualize soft tissues and tumors during treatment, enabling adaptive radiotherapy that adjusts to anatomical changes throughout the course of therapy.

MR-Linac images are typically T2 weighted and are acquired immediately before or during radiation delivery, providing imaging that reflects the patient's current anatomy. Unlike diagnostic MRI, MR-Linac imaging focuses on monitoring tumor position and organ motion to improve targeting accuracy and minimize radiation exposure to healthy tissues.

Accurate segmentation of MR-Linac images is essential for precise tumor targeting and adaptive radiotherapy workflows. However, tumor delineation is challenging due to lower contrast compared to diagnostic MRI.

Automating segmentation with AI can reduce manual contouring efforts, enhance reproducibility, and improve the efficiency of radiotherapy workflows, ultimately contributing to more accurate and personalized pancreatic cancer treatment.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Pancreatic cancer, Magnetic resonance, Linear accelerator, Adaptive radiotherapy, Artificial intelligence, Segmentation

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

See Task 1.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

The website is still under construction but will be found at <https://panther.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

See Task 1.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

See Task 1.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

See Task 1.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

See Task 1.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

See Task 1.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

See Task 1.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval for this project was granted by the ethics committee of the University of Southern Denmark (SDU) under Case no. 20/68031. Additionally, the project is registered with the Regions of Southern Denmark under file no. Journal nr. 20/35211.

All patients provided informed consent allowing their data to be used for MR-Linac related research projects. As a result, ethics approval was required and obtained, and the use of data adheres to established ethical guidelines.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)

- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

See Task 1.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

See Task 1.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The challenge is funded by Radboudumc. Amparo Soeli Betancourt Tarifa acknowledges financial support from Elekta.

Access to the test set labels will be available for the challenge organization team during collection and preparation of the datasets.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training

- Cross-phase

Treatment planning, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Localization, Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this task consists of adult patients (18 years and older) with confirmed pancreatic cancer undergoing radiotherapy using MR-Linac systems. This population includes patients receiving adaptive radiotherapy for localized or borderline resectable pancreatic tumors, where tumor segmentation is critical for precise radiation delivery. The goal is to improve the accuracy and efficiency of tumor and pancreas segmentation during treatment, supporting personalized and adaptive radiotherapy workflows to enhance patient outcomes.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of patients with confirmed pancreatic cancer who have undergone radiotherapy using MR-Linac systems at various stages of treatment. The data includes T2 weighted MR-Linac images acquired during radiotherapy sessions, reflecting the anatomical state of the pancreas and tumor at the time of treatment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The imaging technique used in this task is T2 weighted magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) acquired during MR-Linac radiotherapy sessions. All images are acquired in the axial plane to ensure consistency in anatomical representation during treatment.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Manually annotated segmentations of the tumor will be provided for all patients in the public training cohort.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Pancreas shown in T2 weighted MR-Linac scans of the abdomen, acquired during radiotherapy sessions. Both the challenge cohort and the target cohort consist of patients with confirmed pancreatic cancer undergoing MR-Linac guided adaptive radiotherapy. The imaging focuses on the upper abdomen, capturing the pancreas and surrounding structures.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The participating algorithms output target is the Segmentation of pancreatic tumor lesions.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Develop highly accurate segmentation algorithms for pancreatic tumor lesions in MRI scans. Achieve fast prediction times to ensure models can be seamlessly integrated into clinical workflows, while minimizing computational resource consumption.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

This task data was acquired using Elekta Unity MR-Linac systems with a 1.5T MRI scanner by Philips Healthcare.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All scans were acquired using a T2 weighted MRI protocol on Elekta Unity MR-Linac systems during radiotherapy sessions.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

This retrospective study includes MR-Linac MRI scans acquired at Odense University Hospital during radiotherapy sessions.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All acquisitions were performed by trained radiotherapy radiographers with experience in MR-Linac imaging protocols.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in this task refers to a single T2 weighted MR-Linac image acquired during a radiotherapy session. Each case represents an individual imaging instance that is processed to segment the tumor, with results compared to corresponding expert annotations.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

- Training Set: 50 cases (1 image per patient)
- Validation Set: 5 cases (1 image per patient)
- Testing Set: 30 cases (1 image per patient)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The chosen data distribution ensures a balanced approach to model development, validation, and robust evaluation:

- Training (50 cases-60%) – A larger portion is allocated to training to ensure the model has sufficient data to learn from diverse cases and variations in tumor presentation. This aims to maximize the model's ability to generalize across different patients.
- Validation (5 cases-~5%) – A small validation set provides participants with means to test the submission process and possibly adjust their models without significantly impacting the overall evaluation.
- Testing (30 cases-~35%) – Given the limited number of available images, this allocation represents an optimal balance between providing enough cases for robust evaluation and preserving sufficient samples for effective training and validation.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

- Training Set:

The training set consists of patients with pancreatic tumors. Each case includes T2-weighted MR-Linac images acquired during radiotherapy sessions. This dataset captures a range of tumor sizes and anatomical complexities, reflecting the diversity encountered in real treatment settings.

- Validation and Test Sets:

The validation and test sets will include recent MR-Linac scans from pancreatic cancer patients, reflecting the latest imaging protocols and scanner technologies. The test set is specifically designed to include cases with varying tumor sizes and locations, ensuring the evaluation of algorithm performance

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All data used in this challenge consists of unpublished and previously unseen MRI scans. The dataset includes approximately 85 cases, covering the full training, validation, and test sets.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The gross tumor volume (GTV) was manually delineated on the planning MRI scans by an experienced radiation oncologist. These delineations were then propagated to the MR-Linac scans for each treatment image using deformable image registration.

For each image, the propagated contours were manually adjusted by the oncologist or physician present during the radiotherapy session, ensuring alignment with the visible tumor on the MR-Linac scan, following standard clinical workflow protocols.

Additionally, for the test set, an independent segmentation is performed by a radiologist or radiation oncologist. This second annotation enables the measurement of inter-rater variability and the creation of a consensus ground truth for robust evaluation.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if

necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotations used for this task were created as part of routine clinical practice for MR-Linac guided radiotherapy. As such, annotators followed standard clinical protocols established for tumor delineation in pancreatic cancer patients.

Guidelines:

- Annotators were experienced radiation oncologists trained in GTV delineation for MR-guided adaptive radiotherapy.
- The annotation process adhered to the institution's radiotherapy workflow and followed international guidelines for target volume contouring in pancreatic cancer.
- Annotations were based on planning MRIs and adjusted on each treatment fraction using deformable registration. Manual corrections were made by the oncologist present during treatment to ensure the contours reflected the visible tumor and pancreas anatomy on the MR-Linac scan.
- For the test set, an additional physician is instructed to independently delineate the tumor, ensuring consistency with these established protocols.

Software

- Annotations were performed using dedicated radiotherapy planning software integrated with the Elekta Unity MR-Linac system.
- Additional annotations for the test set are carried out using the developed reader study in the grand-challenge platform, which is also used in Task 1, facilitating independent evaluation and consensus generation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The annotations used in this task were created by experienced radiation oncologists as part of standard clinical practice for MR-Linac guided adaptive radiotherapy. Additionally the test set is also annotated by an experienced radiation oncologist or radiologist.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

See Task 1.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raw training, validation, and testing data are converted from DICOM to MHA format to reduce dataset size and undergo an anonymization process. No additional pre-processing is applied.

Participants are responsible for defining their own pre-processing pipelines to suit their models.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The annotations were created during routine MR-Linac guided radiotherapy following established clinical protocols. Despite high-quality standards, the following error sources are possible:

1. Inter-annotator Variability: Differences between radiation oncologists in interpreting MR images, particularly in challenging cases with poor tumor visibility.
2. Imaging Quality: Motion artifacts and low soft-tissue contrast in MR-Linac scans can result in errors, particularly in poorly defined regions.
3. Manual Corrections: On-the-fly adjustments during treatment may lead to variability, depending on visibility and time constraints.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

See Task 1.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

See Task 1 .

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

See Task 1 .

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

See Task 1 .

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

See Task 1.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

See Task 1 .

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or

- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

See Task 1 .

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

See Task 1 .

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A